

Portfolio assessment in mathematics promotes active learning

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Abstract

This paper introduces a portfolio assessment in mathematics for first-year engineering students that was implemented at the University of Agder (UiA) in 2022. The portfolio consists of two key components, contributing 60% and 40% of the final grade, respectively:

1. Four computer-aided assessment (CAA) tests under supervision, providing immediate feedback on the students' performance. The students can take each test up to four times, with their best attempt counting toward their final grade.
2. A written assignment, where students apply mathematical concepts from the curriculum to solve an engineering problem.

We observe that the students take advantage of multiple test attempts, and that after each test, they organically form groups to discuss the problems with each other. Additionally, the university's math support center sees increased usage during test periods. Biggs et al. (2007) claim that learning is a result of what the student does and that active students foster deep learning. We argue that this assessment design encourages the students to become active in their own learning.

The written assignment also helps students to relate mathematical competence to realistic engineering problems, thus making the subject more relevant to their studies. We claim that this competence is equally important for engineers as it is to solve difficult calculus problems by hand.

Introduction

At the University of Agder (UiA), mathematics is a common course for all engineering programs, with approximately 400 students enrolled each year. The course has traditionally concluded with a high-stake final exam, leading to considerable stress and a failure rate of around 40%. Although there is mandatory coursework, it is completed with varying levels of commitment.

Several studies have highlighted the benefits of active learning at universities. For instance, Biggs et al. (2007) argue that all types of students benefit from active learning, emphasizing that it is the nature of their engagement—what students actually do during the learning process—that significantly impacts their learning. Similarly, Freeman et al. (2014) found that students in STEM fields achieve better outcomes in courses that incorporate active learning compared to traditional lecture-based instruction.

Our analysis of the traditional approach to teaching mathematics—which involves large lectures, problem-solving sessions, and a high-stakes, closed-book exam at the end of the semester—reveals that students often engage passively in their own learning (Zakariya et al., 2022). Students report receiving minimal feedback throughout the course, which

contributes to a high failure rate. One suggestion from Zakariya et al. (2022) was to develop low stake testing to foster learning.

We believe that all students are capable of learning mathematics sufficiently as required to achieve an engineering degree. However, the amount of effort required varies from student to student. To support 400 students in successfully completing the course, it is essential to activate them at the beginning of the semester, helping them understand their current skill level early on and adjust their workload accordingly. With this mindset, we developed a new assessment system designed to motivate students to engage with mathematics earlier in the semester, and at the same time keep the academic quality of the student's mathematical education.

This paper presents the portfolio assessment model, including an example of a digital test exercise and learning outcomes. The data includes student grade outcomes and anecdotal feedback gathered through student quotes.

We developed a new assessment method during a one-week design sprint

The structure of the new assessment method was created through close collaboration between academic staff, university administration, and insights gathered from student interviews. By bringing all stakeholder together to focus on a shared problem, we were able to identify the motivations, perspectives, and requirements of each group involved in the process:

- (1) Academic staff wanted to increase student engagement in the course and promote deeper learning of mathematics. They recognized that the assessment form is the biggest motivator for students' activities, and that mandatory home assignments were often done with different levels of effort. While frequent testing is an effective motivator, such tests typically assess only procedural skills. The staff also aimed to help students understand how to apply mathematics in engineering contexts and to foster more reflection. To address these goals, an individual written assignment was introduced to assess conceptual understanding and application. Lowering the difficulty of the final exam to increase pass rates was not considered a viable option.
- (2) University administration focused on respecting students' rights in assessment. For written tests under supervision, students must be offered multiple opportunities—at least three—to pass. A shared concern with academic staff was the considerable time spent grading. With 400 students, repeated testing, and multiple attempts per student, it became clear that digital assessments with automatic grading was the only practical solution.
- (3) Students supported the idea of multiple tests with multiple tries. However, they were clear about the need for deadlines between tests to avoid procrastination. Their experience with unsupervised home exams during the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the necessity of supervision. Cheating was seen as unavoidable in

unsupervised settings—not only frustrating for instructors but also unfair to students who followed the rules.

The assessment consists of four digital tests and one written assignment

The design sprint resulted in a portfolio-based assessment model, consisting of four supervised computer-aided assessment (CAA) tests and one individual written assignment, as illustrated in Figure 1. Each test can be attempted up to four times, with testing opportunities spread across four two-week periods throughout the semester. Students can earn a maximum of 100 points, with 40 points required to pass the course. There is no minimum score required on any single component; only the total score determines whether a student passes.

Figure 1. Overview of the portfolio-based assessment model for the first mathematics course for engineering students at UiA.

We developed our own customized CAA tests using the STACK assessment tool (STACK, 2025). Figure 2 shows an example of a typical test question. Questions are selected from a database, with randomized numerical values to prevent students from simply memorizing answers. With sufficiently large database of questions, we believe the most effective way for students to succeed on these tests is by genuinely learning the mathematical methods required to solve the problems.

Spørsmål **2**

Ikke besvart ennå

Karakter av maks 3.00

🚩 Marker spørsmål

⚙️ Rediger spørsmål

Tidy STACK question tool | Question tests & deployed variants

Finn real- og imaginærdelen til det komplekse tallet

$$z = (-4 \cdot i - 2)(6 - 5 \cdot i)(-i - 1).$$

$Re(z) =$

$Im(z) =$

Figure 2. Example question from one of the four digital tests. Translated from Norwegian: “Find the real and imaginary part of the complex number.”

The written assignment presents an engineering problem that requires students to apply the mathematical models taught in the course. Students are expected not only to solve the problem but also to reflect on how their solution connects to the mathematics curriculum. This helps them present their mathematical understanding within a context more familiar and relevant than abstract theory alone.

Initially, the written assignment was the same for all engineering students but has since been adapted to reflect the specific contexts of each engineering discipline—civil engineering, renewable energy, mechatronics, electrical engineering, and computer science. This tailored approach fosters a deeper understanding of mathematics within each field, an aspect that was often lacking when assessment was limited to a single final exam.

Mathematics is not purely about mastering procedures and formulas. Niss et al. (2011) argues that learning mathematics should develop a wider set of mathematical competencies that enable students to understand, apply, and reflect on mathematics in meaningful ways. These competencies cannot be fully assessed through a single evaluation method. The portfolio assessment addresses this limitation by allowing us to evaluate a wider range of competencies than was possible with a single end-of-semester exam.

The students’ grades improved significantly

The portfolio assessment was introduced in 2022, resulting in a significant drop in failure rates—from approximately 40% to 10–20%, as shown in Figure 3. From 2014 to 2021, assessment was based on a single end-of-semester exam, with up to two retake opportunities. The figure presents the result from the students’ first attempt. After the introduction of the portfolio assessment, the failure rate dropped significantly. The sharp decrease in 2020 was due to the use of a home exam format during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 3. Failure rate in mathematics for first-year students. The portfolio assessment was introduced in 2022. The exam in 2020 was a home exam due to COVID-19.

Reflections on learning outcomes

There are many factors to consider when evaluating whether this form of assessment improves student learning outcomes. While this paper does not attempt to draw definitive conclusions, it offers several observations—primarily from *MatRIC* (2025), a student-driven center focused on supporting students in their studies.

The support center has reported an increase in students seeking help around test periods—not only beforehand, to prepare, but also afterward, to reflect on mistakes and deepen their understanding of the curriculum (Gjesteland, 2025). Immediate feedback and the opportunity for retakes encourage students to actively engage with the material and seek improvement. In contrast, traditional exams typically provide grades after a delay of up to three weeks—too late for most students to reflect meaningfully on their performance or identify areas for improvement.

In the first year of implementing the portfolio assessment, students tended to collect all available exam questions and focus exclusively on those, rather than studying the broader curriculum. At the time, the exercise database was relatively small, making this strategy effective. However, as the database has grown, this approach has become less viable. In any case, the increased number of tests has led to greater student engagement. As one student reflected: *“We think we’re fooling you [professors] by collecting all the exam questions and only working on those—but in reality, you’re fooling us into doing more math.”*

While students occasionally find shortcuts to solve problems, we believe that, overall, the system encourages them to learn the underlying mathematical methods rather than simply memorizing procedures.

The written assignment fosters a deeper level of mathematical understanding than standard exercises. As one student noted: *“I didn’t really understand the relevance of the digital tests until I started working on the written assignment.”* We believe this higher

level of understanding is achieved when students work independently—without relying on chatbots or similar aids. To ensure authenticity and assess true understanding, we are considering replacing the evaluation of written assignments with oral examinations.

Concluding remarks

We have developed a new assessment method that targets a broader range of mathematical competencies beyond simply mastering procedures and formulas. This approach has improved student grades and increases their engagement throughout the semester, particularly during testing periods. However, there is still work to be done. We need to continuously expand the task database to prevent memorization of exercises. Additionally, we must ensure that students work independently and reflect thoughtfully on their written assignments to develop the mathematical competencies expected of engineers.

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